

Supplementary Information of the article **Telomere length vary with sex, hatching rank and year of birth in little owls, *Athene noctua***

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1. Amplification of telomere repeats using q-PCR methodology

The protocol for DNA extraction from feathers provided us with sufficient amount of DNA to run both sexing and telomere determinations. One to three feathers per individual were selected and a 0.5-1 cm piece from each feather were cut in small pieces with a sterilized scissor. After digestion, feather quills will remain unlysed. For samples containing unlysed quills, we centrifuge briefly and we transfer the supernatant to another tube before proceeding with step 4 of the standard protocol.

Individual relative telomere length (RTL) were obtained following the qPCR methodology previously used in several bird species by our group (*e.g.* Criscuolo et al. 2009, Bize et al. 2009, Criscuolo et al. 2020, Chatelain et al. 2021). DNA quantity and quality were assessed based on spectrophotometer absorbance (Nano-Drop 1000, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA, ratios A260/280 and A260/230) and gel migration. Individual DNA were all diluted to a concentration of 5.0 ng/ μ L, and further used for RTL determination by qPCR. To control for variation in DNA concentrations among diluted samples (due to potential pipetting errors), which may induce a methodological bias to the final RTL values, we amplified, for each individual, a genomic DNA sequence, defined so far as non-variable in copy numbers. The gene used in our species was RAG-1 gene (recombination activating protein 1 gene, NCBI number EU348872.1). Amplifications were conducted in two 384 wells-plates filled by a calibrated automated liquid handling workstation (Epmotion, Eppendorf, Montesson, France), using one distinct plate for control gene and telomere amplifications, due to the different qPCR conditions due to primers sequences properties. Conditions of amplification were 2 min at 95°C followed by 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 30 s at 56°C and 1 min at 72°C (control gene) and of 2 min at 95°C followed by 30 cycles of 15 s at 95°C, 30 s at 56°C and 30 sec at 72°C, (telomere sequence). Reactions were done in a master mix prepared for each primer set, with 5 μ L GoTaq QPCR Mix (Promega, Madison, WI, USA). We used 10 ng of DNA (in a volume of 2 μ L), to which we added the telomere primers at a concentration of 200 nM or the control gene primers at 400 nM (for a final reaction volume of 10 μ L in each well, completed with ultra-pure water). In both plates (control gene and telomere sequences) we amplified individuals' DNA samples plus three quality control references. A DNA golden sample (as a mix of 22 individual samples randomly chosen) that was used as the reference value of 1 for RTL calculations. A dilution curve obtained from the amplification of a randomly chosen reference sample that was serially diluted (from 10 to 0.625 ng/mL). Dilution curves enable us to assess quality of control gene and telomere sequences qPCR amplifications (*i.e.* efficiency values (control gene 0.999; telomere sequences 0.993) and r^2 (0.993 and 0.995, respectively) of the dilution curves). A negative control sample (ultra-pure water) to control for putative contaminations of non-bird DNA. All runs ended by a fusion curve to verify the absence of non-specific amplifications. RTL values were calculated following Pfaffl (2001), shortly as the ratio between Telomere (T) and Control gene (S) Cq values, controlled for their respective amplification efficiencies and expressed relatively to the golden sample T/S value of 1. All samples were run in duplicates

47 and intra-individual repeatability of RTL, evaluated using the Intra Class Coefficient
 48 (Eisenberg *et al.*, 2020), was of 0.769.

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50 **Table S1. Top models set for models of SMI.** For continuous variables, each value
 51 represents the estimate of the effect; for categorical variables, there is a “+” when the variable
 52 is retained in a model.

53 df = degree of freedom. delta = difference of AICc with the model with the lowest AICc.

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Intercept	Nestling number	Proportion of meadows and orchards	Sex	df	AICc	delta
125.8		14.44		4	1057.3	0.00
145.3	-3.52			4	1058.0	0.70
136.7	-2.66	11.93		5	1058.1	0.82
132.3				3	1058.3	0.93
125.3		14.32	+	5	1058.9	1.59

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56 **Figure S1. Forest-plot of estimates for the average model from Table S1.** Reference level
 57 for sex is females.

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61 **Table S2. Top models set for models of RTL.** For continuous variables, each value
 62 represents the estimate of the effect; for categorical variables, there is a “+” when the variable
 63 is retained in a model.
 64 df = degree of freedom. delta = difference of AICc with the model with the lowest AICc.
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Intercept	Proportion of meadows and orchards	Nestling age	Cohort	Rank	Sex	SMI	df	AICc	delta
-0.82			+	+	+	0.0049	12	103.8	0.00
-0.86				+	+	0.0046	9	104.6	0.81
-1.16		0.019	+	+	+	0.0047	13	104.6	0.83
-0.84	-0.17		+	+	+	0.0055	13	104.9	1.12
-0.86			+	+		0.0046	11	105.3	1.46
-1.23	-0.20	0.021	+	+	+	0.0054	14	105.3	1.48

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Supplementary references

- 70 Bize, P., Criscuolo, F., Metcalfe, N.B., Nasir, L. & Monaghan, P. 2009. Telomere dynamics rather than
 71 age predict life expectancy in the wild. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. B* **276**: 1679–1683.
- 72 Chatelain, M., Massemin, S., Zahn, S., Kurek, E., Bulska, E. & Szulkin, M. 2021. Urban metal pollution
 73 explains variation in reproductive outputs in great tits and blue tits. *Science of The Total*
 74 *Environment* **776**: 145966.
- 75 Criscuolo, F., Bize, P., Nasir, L., Metcalfe, N.B., Foote, C.G., Griffiths, K., *et al.* 2009. Real-time
 76 quantitative PCR assay for measurement of avian telomeres. *Journal of Avian Biology* **40**:
 77 342–347.
- 78 Criscuolo, F., Torres, R., Zahn, S. & Williams, T.D. 2020. Telomere dynamics from hatching to sexual
 79 maturity and maternal effects in the ‘multivariate egg.’ *Journal of Experimental Biology* **223**:
 80 jeb232496.
- 81 Eisenberg, D., Nettle, D. & Verhulst, S. 2020. How to calculate the repeatability (ICC) of telomere
 82 length measures.
- 83 Pfaffl, M.W. 2001. A new mathematical model for relative quantification in real-time RT–PCR. *Nucleic*
 84 *Acids Research* **29**: e45.

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